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Deep-sea minerals: a big challenge for the world sustainable future

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Introduction

Minerals are major geopolitical players in today's world, facing the European and international research and sustainable development plans. Supply chains for strategic and critical raw materials such as cobalt, copper, lithium, nickel and rare earth elements are highly concentrated, creating risks. Demographic pressure on the environment and the exhausted status of many of the onshore mineral deposits, is leading to new developments to explore the seabed, from coastal areas to the deep abyssal plains. Spanning a large diversity of environments and resource style, including high and low temperature hydrothermal deposits (SMS, SEDEX), phosphorites, as well as ferromanganese crust and nodules, deep-sea deposits are particularly attractive for their polymetallic nature with high content of transition, rare and critical metals. The attractiveness and development of many of these deposits is hindered by the lack of constrain of their spatial variability, their continuity over area sufficient to sustain potential mining activity, and our poor understanding of the disturbance of marine environments associated with human activities. The International Seabed Authority (ISA) is the intergovernmental regulator of the exploration and future exploitation of seabed minerals beyond national jurisdictions. The Clarion-Clipperton Zone in the Pacific Ocean, the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and the Pacific Prime Crust Zone concentrate most of the exploration contracts with ISA for polymetallic nodules, sulphides and cobalt-rich crusts respectively. In Europe the EC is funding transnational projects (e.g., GeoERA, EMODnet-Geology, GSEU, TRIDENT, S34i) contributing to the best use and management of the subsurface including the seabed raw materials (González et al., 2023). The objective is to provide a better and more accurate basis for future exploration and exploitation, as well as sea-use management, and to provide high quality marine mineral intelligence data to the European data portals. The international community needs to increase knowledge about the seas and oceans prior to any commercial mining contract. New investments in exploration and research, including transdisciplinary studies on the geosphere, biosphere and hydrosphere, regulatory framework, spatial planning, social license and the development of more sustainable mining techniques are necessary to face this enormous challenge for humanity.

References

González, F.J., Medialdea, T. et al. (2023). MINDeSEA – exploring seabed mineral deposits in European seas, metallogeny and geological potential for strategic and critical raw materials. Geological Society, London, Special Publications, 526, <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP526-2022-150>